

Development and optimization of a lightweight LSTM model for battery state-of-charge estimation

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Abstract—The use of machine learning algorithms for battery state-of-charge (SoC) estimation is well established, with a variety of approaches that demonstrate great accuracy. However, two common issues appear. Firstly, datasets might not be large or diverse enough to truly evaluate the proposed approaches. Secondly, the computing cost is very often not taken into consideration. To address these concerns, a lightweight approach using Long-Short-Term-Memory (LSTM) neural networks is proposed for battery SoC estimation. This approach is applied to the NASA Prognostics Center of Excellence randomized battery usage dataset, comprising of 28 batteries subjected to 7 different cycling profiles. After isolating the random walk sequences of the cycling profiles, multiple LSTM networks were trained under different settings, targeting the battery SoC. Our results demonstrate that our method of selectively reducing the resolution of input data enables the proposed models to achieve high accuracy at a low computational cost.

Index Terms—Long Short Term Memory, Battery State of Charge, Machine Learning

I. INTRODUCTION

State-of-Charge (SoC) estimation is a key output of Battery Management Systems (BMS), informing the user of the remaining available energy in the battery or, in the case of battery electric vehicles, the car's effective range. To accurately estimate the battery's recoverable energy, a simple voltage measurement is insufficient, due to memory and hysteresis effects [1]. While To improve accuracy and account for measurement errors and nonlinear effects, increasingly sophisticated algorithms are employed, ranging from basic Coulomb counting [2] to Extended Kalman Filters (EKF) and Neural Networks (NN) [3].

In general, a battery SoC estimation model, algorithm, or method needs to balance between accuracy, generalizability,

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and lightweightness. Additional concerns may be data privacy or resilience to noisy measurements. The models presented and compared in this paper performed impressively:

- Accuracy: The RMSE (Root Mean Square Error) and MAE (Mean Average Error) of the models hover around 1% and 0.4% SoC respectively. Most papers in the related work aim for an RMSE below 2%.
- Generalizability: The models generalize well on a diverse set of battery random walk profiles.
- Lightweightness: Our baseline model with 64 units, 7 inputs and a 60 step input horizon trained at 30seconds per epoch, on a Ryzen 5 5600X 6-Core processor in a dataset with 152887 train samples and 53469 validation samples. Equivalent GPU time is 1-3seconds, depending on the GPU.
- Data privacy: Data privacy is not part of this study.
- Resilience to noisy measurements: Model architecture (using mean and median values over a long time frame) is resilient to short term sensor noise, and results indicate good results even in the unfiltered dataset. However, for a more straightforward intercomparison between the models, some of the study takes place in a subset of the dataset comprising of 97% of the full dataset.

The main contributions of this paper are as follows:

- We demonstrate that a dataset traditionally used for SoH estimation can be effectively repurposed for SoC estimation.
- We introduce a selective data resolution reduction strategy that significantly decreases training time while preserving estimation accuracy.
- We validate the proposed approach on the most challenging segments of a noisy, real-world dataset, where SoC values must be inferred rather than directly measured.

II. RELATED WORK

There is a relative dearth of open source battery cycling data, and neither the cycling method nor the data logging framework is standardized [4]. This complicates the comparison of methods and results, with most approaches being, by necessity, dataset-specific. The initial paper has been widely cited, with many authors leveraging the dataset to work on State-of-Health (SoH) estimation and degradation, but relatively few working on SoC estimation. Bavant et al. [5] utilize the Adam optimization algorithm and SoC-OCV curves to estimate both SoH and SoC for each cell of the dataset, but their statistical approach is not, by definition, generalizable. Also, their model is not evaluated for autoregressive performance. Alamin et al. [6] use the dataset to create a digital twin for electric vehicle batteries. They compare three training approaches (Random Forest, Light Gradient Boosting and Deep Neural Network) for both SoH and SoC estimation. They settle on a framework of calculating SoH first, and periodically retraining the SoC estimator. Since their goal is a digital twin however, they evaluate their model on its ability to infer the current status of the battery and not its ability to predict its future state. Finally, Nascimento et al. [7] use a hybrid (physics informed) model to estimate output voltage. According to this work, utilization of materials science knowledge reduces the difficulty of the data-driven approach, while estimation of output voltage only is an intermediate step to full estimation of SoC.

Moving away from the particular dataset, Benallal et al. [8] introduced an LSTM model on a dataset they developed, and utilized hyperband-driven hyperparameter optimization to increase its accuracy. Since their focus is vehicle BMS, they chose to cycle their batteries using variable discharging loads, with no random walking, reducing complexity. Tabine et al. [9] used a much simpler polynomial fitting model with great results, but their focus was on the effect of temperature only and the usage of simulated data absolved the model of having to compensate for measurement errors. Finally, Yun et al. [10], working on synthetic data, utilized an adaptive EKF model to improve the accuracy of SoC estimation by effectively segmenting the SoC/Voltage curve.

Taken together, although a substantial body of work exists on state-of-charge estimation, most approaches are tightly coupled to specific datasets, operating conditions, or modeling assumptions. Moreover, many existing studies rely on curated or synthetic load profiles, physics-informed models, or computationally intensive architectures, which may limit their applicability and generalization to noisy, real-world scenarios with diverse and dynamic usage patterns.

III. DATASET DESCRIPTION AND CURATION

The dataset comprises of cycling data for 28 battery cells, distinguished by the presence of supercycles [11]. Every supercycle comprises of two full charge and discharge cycles, followed by one full but intermittent charge and discharge cycle. Afterwards, a random walk starts, comprised of one or five minutes of constant current steps, shortened when the

battery reaches its cut-off voltage, 4.2V for charging or 3.2V for discharging respectively. The random walk sequence stops at 50 random walk cycles (with the exception of Group 1). The 28 battery cells are organized in groups of four, each one subjected to the following conditions [11]:

- Group 1: Pure random walk at 25°C, five minute steps, up to 1500 cycles (about 5 days).
- Group 2: Full charge to 4.2V, random walk to 3.2V, five minute steps, 25°C.
- Group 3: Full discharge to 3.2V, random walk up to 4.2V, five minute steps, 25°C.
- Group 4: Full charge to 4.2V, random walk to 3.2V, one minute steps, emphasis on high current values, 40°C.
- Group 5: Full charge to 4.2V, random walk to 3.2V, one minute steps, emphasis on high current values, 25°C.
- Group 6: Full charge to 4.2V, random walk to 3.2V, one minute steps, emphasis on low current values, 40°C.
- Group 7: Full charge to 4.2V, random walk to 3.2V, one minute steps, emphasis on low current values, 25°C.

The authors of the initial paper featuring the dataset [11] focused on SoH deterioration, while our goal was to work on SoC estimation. This meant that some data were not available and had to be inferred by the current and voltage measurements of the dataset. Accordingly, the following preprocessing steps were applied to the dataset:

- 1) Battery SoH is extracted from the second reference discharge event of every supercycle, and applied to all of the measurements of the supercycle. SoH was calculated twice, as Watt-hours (Wh) and as Ampere-hours (Ah) respectively.
- 2) Every five or one minute period of constant current (step) is compressed to one measurement, registering the start and end voltage of every step, its total energy and its mean temperature. Incomplete steps (the ones which reach cut-off voltage) are also compressed to one measurement. The duration of each step is also registered, since it varies between datasets. This is afterwards utilized as a Δt variable for training. This is a practical approach, used by other authors (e.g. Che et al. [12]) as well.
- 3) Intermediate intervals between each step of the random walk of no current and small duration (1-2 seconds) were ignored completely since they do not influence SoC.
- 4) Every cut-off step at a current below a certain threshold is assigned 100% or 0% SoC at its end, and the next step is assigned the same value at its start. These steps are used as anchor points, avoiding the accumulation of measurement error.
- 5) SoC values for intermediate steps are calculated using interpolation using the total energy and the current of the steps. SoC values were also calculated twice, both as a function of Wh and Ah. In both cases, however, a 0-100 scale was utilized. For the Wh value, an adjustment was made for charging efficiency.
- 6) Non-random walk steps are dropped, and every supercy-

cle forms a continuous time series suitable for training an LSTM model.

The advantages of this preprocessing method are:

- The sharp compression of the dataset (approximately 30 to 1).
- The uniformization of data structure without adulteration of the underlying information, achieved through the Dt variable.
- The inference of SoC and SoH values through a process that conforms to battery physics.
- The smoothing of possible noise measurement by the otherwise necessary averaging.
- The proposed preprocessing pipeline is fully reproducible and can be readily adapted to assess the sensitivity of the results to alternative assumptions or preprocessing choices.

While this preprocessing method has its advantages, challenges could arise if the underlying data had different characteristics:

- The SoC inference process could become less accurate if the random walk segments were much longer (measurement error integration), especially for the Wh version of the SoC.
- The compression is possible because of the nature of the dataset. A different dataset with far more rapid current changes would result in a smaller compression ratio.
- The SoH inference step requires a full charge followed by a full discharge. If the dataset did not have the reference cycles, the SoH variables would have to be calculated differently or not at all.

To summarize, the resolution of the data were selectively reduced in a way that minimizes useful information loss. This method is also used by the creator of the dataset to a much smaller degree, who reduced the resolution of the measurements in some types of charge and discharge events, and is also used in other contexts, such as space trajectory simplification [13] foveated rendering [14], or IoT applications in general [15].

IV. METHODOLOGY

LSTM networks have become a staple of time series modeling due to their ability to capture both short and long term context in time-series data through gated current units [16]. In the context of SoC estimation, short-term context relates to voltage and current fluctuations within a single discharge cycle, whereas long-term context relates to gradual changes in battery chemistry associated to battery aging. Three different types of LSTM networks were developed and compared:

- A canonical [17] LSTM network, trained via backpropagation through time, modeling long-term dependencies in sequential data using gated memory cells designed to prevent vanishing gradients.
- A bidirectional [18] LSTM network, extending the canonical form by processing the input sequence in both

forward and backward directions, improving context representation for each timestep.

- A stacked [19] LSTM network, increasing representational capacity by layering multiple LSTM blocks, allowing the model to capture hierarchical temporal patterns across layers.

The fourth type of LSTM networks, a time-distributed [20] one, which applies shared LSTM operations independently to each time slice or segment of input data allowing for spatial or segment-wise patterns to be captured across time was not tested as it was not appropriate for the nature of the physical problem: SoC is conditional to power/current drain, and predicting multiple steps ahead would effectively be a prediction of the future power/current drain, instead of the state of the battery.

Two figures of merit were selected: RMSE and MAE, both having the unit of the variable under test (%SoC at the end of the sequence). While training seeks to minimize RMSE in the validation dataset as in most machine learning applications, the MAE of the validation dataset is also reported to offer a more interpretable metric for model evaluation to the reader.

To ensure a like-for-like comparison for the models, sometimes we had to restrict either certain cell groups or some sequences from our analysis. In every case:

- The same restrictions were applied to both the training and validation datasets.
- No information leakage was allowed, with restrictions being applied on the training and validation sequences after the sequences are created, using only data from the input features in the input horizon.

Finally, to benchmark the results, we used the common [21] method of training a multi-layer perceptron (MLP) and an XGBoost-based model under the same restrictions of each case study.

V. RESULTS

A. Benchmark Models

While optimizing the MLP and XGBoost models is not the focus of this paper, a fair benchmark is necessary to evaluate the LSTM models. To optimize each model, a default configuration was selected, and the main variables were changed to assess the impact of each configuration variable. We evaluated the models on the full dataset (Groups 1 through 7), training the models on twenty one cells (three from each group) and validating on seven cells (the remaining one from each group). We also evaluated on Groups 4 through 7 (12 training cells, 4 validation cells), and maintained an increase in complexity only when performance increased in both cases. When we afterwards changed the input window or restricted the analysis to specific parts of the dataset, we maintained the same configuration for benchmarking. The sklearn Python library's MLPRegressor function was used for the benchmark MLP models while the XGBRegressor function of xgboost Python library was used for the XGBoost models.

TABLE I
MLPREGRESSOR CONFIGURATION RELATIVE TO DEFAULT SKLEARN
LIBRARY VALUES

Variable	Default Value	Selected Value
hidden_layer_sizes	(100)	(128,64)
max_iter	200	400
n_iter_no_change	10	20

TABLE II
XGBREGRESSOR CONFIGURATION RELATIVE TO DEFAULT XGBOOST
LIBRARY VALUES

Variable	Default Value	Selected Value
n_estimators	100	400
learning_rate	0.3	0.05
subsample	1.0	0.9
colsample_bytree	1.0	0.9

1) *MLP model*: For the MLP model, the main benefit was derived by adding a hidden layer. Few adjustments were made (Table I), since most configuration changes led to little or no improvement relative to the default values.

2) *XGBoost models*: For the XGBoost models, the largest improvements relative to the default configuration were made possible by increasing the number of estimators and decreasing the learning rate. Other small adjustments were also made (Table II).

B. Baseline Models

For our baseline models, we trained and validated a canonical LSTM model on three of the cells of every four cell group and validated on the fourth, while an overall model was also trained with the training set including three cells of each group and the validation set the fourth of each group. This allows us to evaluate the data quality of each group. Because groups 1-3 and 4-7 have the same timestep, two models were trained on them as well. In all cases we restricted training and validation to SoH values above 80%, per common practice [22]. The input features used were deltatime (the duration of every compressed time period), median voltage, concluding voltage, median current and two one-shot variable indicating whether the timestep is a charging or a discharging one, with an input horizon of 60 time steps.

We notice that the models tend to fail around 0% and 100% SoC (Figure 1). This is largely a byproduct of the

TABLE III
BASELINE MODELS: RMSE, MAE IN UNFILTERED VALIDATION SET

Group	MLP	XGBoost	LSTM
1	9.49%, 7.15%	11.51%, 9.79%	1.77%, 1.25%
2	4.33%, 3.22%	2.29%, 1.55%	2.10%, 1.41%
3	6.68%, 5.13%	4.66%, 3.43%	4.59%, 3.52%
4	8.80%, 3.79%	4.49%, 1.80%	6.69%, 2.21%
5	5.01%, 2.49%	3.70%, 2.42%	3.79%, 1.42%
6	1.98%, 1.25%	1.81%, 1.28%	1.30%, 0.67%
7	3.50%, 1.82%	3.67%, 1.84%	2.22%, 0.93%
1-3	9.07%, 6.88%	9.12%, 7.33%	2.76%, 1.97%
4-7	4.55%, 1.69%	3.94%, 2.23%	2.64%, 1.05%
1-7	6.09%, 3.13%	6.68%, 4.03%	3.06%, 1.45%

Fig. 1. True SoC vs predicted SoC for groups 1-7 in the unfiltered dataset

TABLE IV
BASELINE MODELS: RMSE, MAE IN FILTERED VALIDATION SET

Group	MLP	XGBoost	LSTM
1	9.03%, 6.89%	11.29%, 9.59%	1.32%, 1.02%
2	4.85%, 3.38%	3.24%, 1.77%	2.74%, 1.36%
3	7.05%, 5.46%	4.87%, 3.72%	3.64%, 2.62%
4	5.81%, 2.58%	4.25%, 1.64%	4.80%, 1.94%
5	2.13%, 1.53%	3.57%, 2.42%	1.03%, 0.72%
6	1.38%, 1.01%	1.66%, 1.21%	0.87%, 0.58%
7	2.69%, 1.58%	3.17%, 1.69%	1.51%, 0.78%
1-3	9.55%, 7.26%	8.94%, 7.26%	2.96%, 2.22%
4-7	3.11%, 1.49%	3.48%, 2.09%	1.26%, 0.74%
1-7	5.94%, 3.29%	6.38%, 3.92%	1.52%, 0.85%

dataset, which includes some charges/discharges cut short by the threshold voltages, sometimes immediately. This causes the voltage and current measurements to be extremely noisy. Excluding sequences for which the last measurements of the target horizon were too short to be trustworthy (3% of the dataset) leads into much better results (Table IV and Figure 2). Visually, on Figure 2, we notice that the conditional exclusion of the prematurely cut-off steps (which are invariably around the 0% or 100% SoC mark) increase accuracy all over the SoC range and not just around the edges.

The following takeaways can be derived from the baseline models:

- The dataset is quite noisy, but still good enough for ML training.
- The simpler (MLP-XGBoost) models do somewhat better, but still worse than the LSTM when the data is not very diverse (i.e. when training and validation take place on only one group). When all groups are included, the LSTM model's ability to understand context causes it to

Fig. 2. True SoC vs predicted SoC for groups 1-7 in the filtered dataset

Fig. 3. True SoC vs predicted SoC for groups 1-7, filtered dataset with SoH(Ah) as a feature.

TABLE V

RMSE, MAE WHEN ADDING FEATURES IN GROUPS 1-7, UNFILTERED DATASET

Added Features	MLP	XGBoost	LSTM
Temp	6.76%, 3.48%	6.31%, 3.80%	2.95%, 1.33%
SoH(Ah)	7.13%, 3.63%	6.76%, 4.22%	2.88%, 1.06%
Temp+SoH(Ah)	7.76%, 4.02%	6.16%, 3.67%	2.76%, 0.99%
SoH(Wh)	5.97%, 3.09%	6.78%, 4.22%	2.91%, 1.21%
Temp+SoH(Wh)	7.45%, 3.86%	6.18%, 3.67%	2.94%, 1.20%

decisively outperform them.

- The problem under study is not trivial - long term dependencies do exist, and are captured by the LSTM model.

C. Feature Selection

To increase model accuracy, more input features can be added: Temperature and the state of health of the battery (extracted by reference cycles that are neither part of the training nor the validation dataset). The models were trained on both the unfiltered and filtered datasets.

We notice temperature is actually making the models worse, possibly because it stays more or less constant for each cell

TABLE VI

RMSE, MAE WHEN ADDING FEATURES IN GROUPS 1-7, FILTERED DATASET

Added Features	MLP	XGBoost	LSTM
Temp	6.44%, 3.48%	5.97%, 3.69%	1.67%, 1.00%
SoH(Ah)	6.17%, 3.30%	6.48%, 4.18%	0.81%, 0.41%
Temp+SoH(Ah)	6.28%, 3.30%	5.78%, 3.56%	1.17%, 0.42%
SoH(Wh)	6.22%, 3.28%	5.89%, 3.57%	1.47%, 0.69%
Temp+SoH(Wh)	5.84%, 3.11%	6.34%, 3.97%	1.55%, 0.80%

group and thus does not vary enough for the model to train on. On the other hand, introducing a SoH variable increases accuracy significantly, but does not rely strictly on the last voltage and current timeseries (Tables V & VI).

D. Time Horizon

We also investigated the effect of shortening or lengthening the input horizon. While a short input horizon undermines model accuracy, its lengthening offers diminishing and past a point negative returns. Optimal length for model training ends up being 60 time steps. The intercomparison was performed with and without SoH as a feature, to explore whether the SoH variable would substitute for the context derived from a longer input horizon. In that regard, SoH helped the LSTM in all cases apart from the use cases with the shortest and longest input horizon, not allowing us to arrive at such a conclusion.

E. Stacked and bidirectional models

A comparison between a stacked, a bidirectional and a canonical LSTM was made, while also varying the number of units of the LSTM layers. No meaningful benefit was extracted by the increase in complexity (in some cases, there was under-performance). This is due to the complexity of the underlying problem: The problem is complex enough to benefit from the LSTM approach (as evidenced by the large benefit derived from the LSTM approach compared to MLP or XGBoost) but not complex enough to warrant the additional complexity of stacked or bidirectional LSTMs. For the bidirectional LSTMs, the time-series offers context (the state of health of the battery and the recent discharge profile) while the last time steps

TABLE VII

RMSE, MAE WHEN VARYING THE LENGTH OF THE TIME HORIZON IN GROUPS 1-7 IN THE FILTERED DATASET

Time Horizon	MLP	XGBoost	LSTM
15	6.89%, 3.85%	7.20%, 4.42%	2.91%, 1.62%
30	5.85%, 3.15%	6.67%, 4.09%	1.74%, 1.06%
45	5.84%, 3.27%	6.47%, 3.98%	1.48%, 0.87%
60	5.94%, 3.29%	6.38%, 3.92%	1.52%, 0.85%
75	5.07%, 2.83%	6.22%, 3.85%	1.75%, 1.00%
90	5.74%, 3.30%	6.09%, 3.79%	1.22%, 0.79%
15 w/SoH	6.91%, 3.91%	5.51%, 4.83%	3.50%, 1.98%
30 w/SoH	6.25%, 3.37%	6.99%, 4.49%	1.49%, 0.83%
45 w/SoH	6.03%, 3.31%	6.59%, 4.19%	1.43%, 0.64%
60 w/SoH	6.17%, 3.30%	6.48%, 4.18%	0.81%, 0.41%
75 w/SoH	5.98%, 3.16%	6.25%, 4.01%	1.10%, 0.49%
90 w/SoH	6.59%, 3.63%	6.04%, 3.90%	1.56%, 0.66%

TABLE VIII

RMSE, MAE WHEN ADDING UNITS OR LAYERS IN THE BASELINE LSTM

LSTM Units	RMSE	MAE	Relative Complexity
32	1.76%	0.89%	0.28
64	0.81%	0.41%	1
96	1.02%	0.43%	2.17
128	1.11%	0.35%	3.78
48,48	1.09%	0.39%	1.59
64,32	1.09%	0.41%	1.67
64,64	0.89%	0.35%	2.79
64,32,16	0.83%	0.49%	1.84
Bi64	1.21%	0.66%	2
Bi64,Bi32	0.88%	0.39%	4.24

of the input horizon offer a more immediate view of the SoC of the battery (the voltage drop under different current drain). Returning the sequences twice does not offer additional information and adds "noise" to the input data. On the other hand, the stacked approach fails to improve on the canonical LSTMs since there is probably not a higher order context to be discovered relative to the canonical LSTMs, a phenomenon that has been observed in other contexts as well [23]. With regards to relative complexity, it is calculated using the widely used [24] $4 \times U \times (U + D + 1)$ formula, where U is the number of LSTM units and D the number of inputs. The networks were trained with an input horizon of 60.

F. Model Runtime

Finally, it is important to compare the training time of the various models. Since all models are early stopping, it is appropriate to also list epoch training times. The values of Table IX correspond to the actual epoch (the median value of each model) and model training times for the full (Groups 1-7) filtered dataset with SoH(Ah) input on a Ryzen 5 5600X 6-Core processor.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The use of ML algorithms for battery SoC estimation is of crucial importance in many applications and a variety of approaches are applied that demonstrate great accuracy. The present study presents a lightweight approach for battery SoC estimation, relying on selectively reducing the resolution of input data. Multiple different Long-Short-Term-Memory

TABLE IX

MODEL PERFORMANCE RELATIVE TO RUNTIME GROUPS 1-7 IN THE FILTERED DATASET

LSTM Units	Input Horizon	RMSE	Epoch Runtime (seconds)	Total runtime (seconds)
64	15	3.50%	9	594
64	30	1.49%	16	1634
64	45	1.43%	23	2200
64	60	0.81%	32	4217
64	75	1.10%	36	4499
64	90	1.56%	42	2771
32	60	1.76%	29	2268
48	60	1.27%	24	3153
96	60	1.02%	50	4437
128	60	1.11%	63	6829
48,48	60	1.09%	55	5450
64,32	60	1.09%	51	4712
64,64	60	0.89%	70	5190
64,32,16	60	0.83%	88	6704
Bi64	60	1.21%	35	2341
Bi64,Bi32	60	0.88%	80	6745

(LSTM) neural networks setups were trained under different settings and data limitations, targeting the battery SoC. Our results demonstrate that the proposed models achieve high accuracy at a low computational cost.

While all LSTM models decisively outperform the MLP and XGBoost benchmarks on the diverse datasets, the canonical LSTM outperforms all other LSTM approaches with a smaller computational cost. This indicates a complex enough problem to warrant the utilization of neural network approach, but not complex enough to require the more complex and more computationally demanding stacked and bidirectional networks.

VII. FURTHER WORK

Further work can be performed in multiple sectors. Firstly, on the same dataset, one could explore whether the models can maintain their accuracy while training under a federated learning framework. This would be challenging due to the heterogeneity of the cycling characteristics of each group. Secondly, one could try to aggregate battery data from multiple different datasets to assess the models' ability to generalize not only with regards to cycling regimens but also different battery types or even technologies. In such a scenario, it would be interesting to see whether stacked LSTM models would outperform canonical ones, since additional layers of context would need to be captured by the neural network.

Another way to expand on this work would be to try to use voltage rather than SoC as a target feature. This would not require making assumptions about SoC made in this paper, making the approach based entirely on primary measurements. On the other hand, this would require voltage to be both an input and a target feature, which would require a different approach to evaluating model performance (predicting just one step ahead would not be challenging enough). A solution in this case would be to try predicting multiple steps ahead using a time-distributed LSTM, while offering the intermediate current or power drain as an additional input feature for the network. Another option would be to use an autoregressive

approach, evaluating the models' ability to avoid integrating error.

REFERENCES

- [1] G. L. Plett, "Extended kalman filtering for battery management systems of lipb-based hev battery packs: Part 1. background," *Journal of Power Sources*, vol. 134, no. 2, pp. 252–261, 2004.
- [2] Y. Zhang, W. Song, S. Lin, and Z. Feng, "A novel model of the initial state of charge estimation for lifepo4 batteries," *Journal of Power Sources*, vol. 248, pp. 1028–1033, 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2013.09.135>
- [3] R. Xiong, J. Cao, Q. Yu, H. He, and F. Sun, "Critical review on the battery state of charge estimation methods for electric vehicles," *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 1832–1843, 2018.
- [4] P. Dini and D. Paolini, "Exploiting artificial neural networks for the state of charge estimation in ev/hv battery systems: A review," *Batteries*, vol. 11, no. 3, p. 107, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/2313-0105/11/3/107>
- [5] A. Bavand, S. A. Khajehoddin, M. Ardakani, and A. Tabesh, "Online estimations of li-ion battery soc and soh applicable to partial charge/discharge," *IEEE Transactions on Transportation Electrification*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 3673–3685, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9747455>
- [6] K. S. S. Alamin, Y. Chen, E. Macii, M. Poncino, and S. Vinco, "A machine learning-based digital twin for electric vehicle battery modeling," in *2022 International Conference on Omni-layer Intelligent Systems (COINS)*. IEEE, 2022, pp. 1–6. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9854960>
- [7] R. G. Nascimento, M. Corbetta, C. S. Kulkarni, and F. A. Viana, "Hybrid physics-informed neural networks for lithium-ion battery modeling and prognosis," *Journal of Power Sources*, vol. 513, p. 230526, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2021.230526>
- [8] A. Benallal, N. Cheggaga, A. Hebib, and A. Ilinca, "Lstm-based state-of-charge estimation and user interface development for lithium-ion battery management," *World Electric Vehicle Journal*, vol. 16, no. 3, p. 168, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/2032-6653/16/3/168>
- [9] A. Tabine, E. M. Laadissi, H. Mastouri, A. Elachhab, S. Bouzaid, and A. Hajjaji, "A novel approach for accurate soc estimation in li-ion batteries in view of temperature variations," *Results in Engineering*, vol. 25, p. 103962, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2025.103962>
- [10] J. Yun, Y. Choi, J. Lee, S. Choi, and C. Shin, "State-of-charge estimation method for lithium-ion batteries using extended kalman filter with adaptive battery parameters," *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 90901–90915, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3305950>
- [11] B. Bole, C. S. Kulkarni, and M. Daigle, "Adaptation of an electrochemistry-based li-ion battery model to account for deterioration observed under randomized use," *Annual Conference of the PHM Society*, vol. 6, no. 1, 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://papers.phmsociety.org/index.php/phmconf/article/view/2490>
- [12] Z. Che, S. Purushotham, K. Cho, D. Sontag, and Y. Liu, "Recurrent neural networks for multivariate time series with missing values," *Scientific Reports*, vol. 8, no. 1, p. 6085, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-018-24271-9>
- [13] N. Meratnia and R. A. de By, "Spatiotemporal compression techniques for moving point objects," in *EDBT 2004 Workshops*. Springer, 2004, pp. 765–782.
- [14] B. Mohanto, A. T. Islam, E. Gobetti, and O. Staadt, "An integrative view of foveated rendering," *Computers & Graphics*, vol. 102, pp. 474–501, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0097849321002211>
- [15] C. Rodriguez-Pabon, G. Riva, C. Zerbini, J. Ruiz-Rosero, G. Ramirez-Gonzalez, and J. C. Corrales, "An adaptive sampling period approach for management of iot energy consumption: Case study approach," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 4, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/22/4/1472>
- [16] K. Greff, R. K. Srivastava, J. Koutník, B. R. Steunebrink, and J. Schmidhuber, "Lstm: A search space odyssey," *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems*, vol. 28, no. 10, pp. 2222–2232, 2017.
- [17] S. Hochreiter and J. Schmidhuber, "Long short-term memory," *Neural Computation*, vol. 9, no. 8, pp. 1735–1780, nov 1997.
- [18] A. Graves and J. Schmidhuber, "Bidirectional LSTM networks for improved phoneme classification and recognition," in *Artificial Neural Networks: Formal Models and Their Applications – ICANN*. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2005, pp. 799–804.
- [19] I. Sutskever, O. Vinyals, and Q. V. Le, "Sequence to sequence learning with neural networks," *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, vol. 27, pp. 3104–3112, 2014.
- [20] H. Qiao, T. Wang, P. Wang, S. Qiao, and L. Zhang, "A time-distributed spatiotemporal feature learning method for machine health monitoring with multi-sensor time series," *Sensors*, vol. 18, no. 9, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/18/9/2932>
- [21] H. Hewamalage, C. Bergmeir, and K. Bandara, "Recurrent neural networks for time series forecasting: Current status and future directions," *International Journal of Forecasting*, vol. 37, no. 1, pp. 388–427, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0169207020300996>
- [22] H. Liu, C. Li, X. Hu, J. Li, K. Zhang, Y. Xie, R. Wu, and Z. Song, "Multi-modal framework for battery state of health evaluation using open-source electric vehicle data," *Nature Communications*, vol. 16, no. 1137, Jan 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-025-56485-7>
- [23] Z. Cui, R. Ke, Z. Pu, and Y. Wang, "Stacked bidirectional and unidirectional lstm recurrent neural network for forecasting network-wide traffic state with missing values," *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, vol. 118, p. 102674, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0968090X20305891>
- [24] A. Graves and J. Schmidhuber, "Framework phoneme classification with bidirectional lstm and other neural network architectures," *Neural Networks*, vol. 18, no. 5, pp. 602–610, 2005, iJCNN 2005. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S089368005001206>